

**IMPACT OF NEIGHBOURHOOD SAFETY ON RESIDENTIAL RENTAL PROPERTY
VACANCY IN BIDA**

¹Saidu U. A., ²Mohammed J. K., ³Nathaniel, S.

Email: ¹saidumadakikamala@gmail.com, ²muhammad.jibrinkatun@fedpolybida.edu.ng,
³nathanielsimon765@gmail.com

^{1,2&3}Department of Estate Management and Valuation, Federal Polytechnic Bida, Niger State.
Correspondence: muhammad.jibrinkatun@fedpolybida.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112925>

Abstract

Safety of residence in an environment is a major priority and consideration by potential occupants of residential properties before making the decision to reside in a building or an environment. This study examined the impact of neighbourhood safety on residential rental property vacancy in Bida, Nigeria. A quantitative approach was adopted with administration of questionnaire on residents of rental properties from three neighbourhood densities (high, medium and low) across the study area. The collected data were analysed descriptively and presented in frequency tables while relative importance index (RII) was used to rank the determinants of residential rental vacancy. Findings of this study revealed that high level of gang activities, burglary of homes alongside unsecured vacant properties are the most common security concerns across the study area. It was also found that area 8 had the highest vacancy rate with 8.7%, followed by Dokodza with 4.89%, while FMC quarters has the lowest vacancy rate of residential rental properties in the study area with 4.78%. Poor location, property condition and age alongside accessibility were the highest ranked determinants of vacancy rate of rental properties with RII values above 0.72. The finding from the regression analysis indicated that vacancy of rental properties in Dokodza and Area 8 are significantly impacted by neighbourhood safety with p-value below 0.005 (.043 and .041 respectively) while neighbourhood security is not significant as a determinant of vacancy rate in FMC quarters (p-value = 0.667). The study therefore concluded that, neighbourhood security has a significant impact on vacancy of residential rental properties with other underlying factors peculiar to low density neighbourhoods. It was recommended that property owners and policy makers should prioritise routine surveillance and patrols alongside investment in advance security infrastructures to enhance safety and reduce vacancies.

Keywords: Neighbourhood, Safety, Residential, Rental properties, Vacancy rate.

1.0 Background to the Study

In real estate marketing, before setting up a building for profitable purposes the safety of the occupants must be put into consideration. The lack of safety in urban area has increased worldwide in the last decade at a rate that has largely surpassed that of urbanization (Gerten et al., 2019). According to Akinbobola (2022), 31% of the entire 437,000 global crime incidence are reported from Africa. Across many Nigerian states, the capacity of the police to maintain law and order has continued to be undermined by the rapidly growing incidence of violent crimes (Ojo & Ojewale, 2019; Adewale et al., 2020). Incidences of burglary of homes, bullying and harassment as well as kidnapping have drastically increased in many parts of Nigeria.

However, the lack of proper and sufficient infrastructure and public services “proper sanitation, housing, education and health care” to support the growing population of residential neighbourhoods do not only lead to the growth of slums, but also breeds discontent among urban dwellers, leading to unsafe conditions (Malik et al., 2020; Owusu-Ansah & Asante, 2022). The prevalent incidence of nuisance and traffic safety in urban areas has made some people abandon some environment while others perceive such areas as dangerous. It is this perceived danger and growing threats, alongside the inability of the police to provide adequate protection that have led to the emergence of neighbourhood safety (Vitale, 2021; Toohey & Taylor, 2023). Therefore, the significance of adequate housing to the social well-being of the people in any society cannot be overemphasized (Dauda, 2024). However, housing and neighbourhood are inseparable, because it is not just about the floor space; it is about the vibe of the area, the neighbors, the amenities, schools, friends, shops and parks, transit or traffic (Opit et al., 2020).

In urban areas, where rate at which various crimes are being committed alongside inadequate supply and provision of basic infrastructure, as well as weak enforcement of law remains crucial in the discussion of housing stability, further underscoring the relationship between neighbourhood safety and vacancy rate (Weimann & Oni, 2019). Secure locations often convince occupants of residential properties due to its secure and serene nature in the face of worries, thereby enhancing the growth of vacancy in other high-risk neighbourhoods (Babalola et al., 2020; Nwachukwu, 2023). Adu-Gyamfi et al. (2022) posited that the attractiveness of real property is influenced by security concerns like burglary, gang activities, thefts, and other various criminal activities alongside concerns for environmental safety. As a result of this, owners of residential properties in an unsecure environment always find it hard to pull in and keep occupants, thus infringing negatively on rental returns and general housing market (Babalola et al., 2020). On the contrary, neighbourhoods with adequate security infrastructures and close connection between residents of the community through engagement have the possibility of experiencing reduction in the rate of residential property vacancy since occupants of buildings in such neighbourhoods have greater sense of security, stability and belonging (Barreca et al., 2020; Agheyisi & Aghedo, 2021).

In some developing countries, neighbourhood safety has been one of the factors affecting the rate of vacancy in property (Wei and Ewing 2018). A vacant property is one that has been unoccupied for an extended period of time. In many developed and developing nations, the prevalence of vacant properties has been a course of concern due to its many implications on investment returns and the national economy (Tien, 2019). Ogbewe and Ayodele (2023) highlighted that Nigeria's

Saidu U. A., Mohammed J. K., Nathaniel, S.

housing vacancy rates continues to rise annually while many cities across the country, particularly Abuja, flaunt empty unaffordable houses.

Nigeria in recent times has witnessed an unprecedented level of insecurity and safety challenges. This has made national safety threat to be a major issue for the government and has prompted huge allocation of the national budget to safety (Odalonu, 2022). The United Nations unveiled that most countries of the developing economy spend an average of between 9% and 14% of their annual budgets on safety measures (Olajide and Lizam, 2016). Neighbourhood safety is a communal safety scheme in which people living within a community voluntarily agree to take responsibility of the security of lives and properties of one another. It ranges from traditional or conventional modes of military power and the essence is to mediate street harassment and anxiety experienced while outside the home (Kilculle 2015; Choi & Lee, 2021; Bourke, 2022). Many times, economy challenges, ethnic and religious conflicts and unmanaged advancement of science and technology may influence insecurity and threaten lives of people.

Meanwhile, residents of unsafe neighbourhoods frequently report poor health for a variety of reasons, including the fact that these neighbourhoods can lead to chronic stress, which can exhaust people's ability to manage life's everyday stressors (Robinette et al., 2021). This has transit to residents vacating unsafe neighbourhoods for safety reasons there by leaving properties vacant and void. However, many scholars have tried to provide a solution to the problem of neighborhood safety on property vacancy rate by conducting different research. For instance, Kiggins and Pavol (2023) researched on the effect of neighborhood safety on childhood mental and behavioral health problems, findings from the study shows that poverty levels did have a significant impact on mental, behavioral, and emotional well-being. Timperio et al., (2015) assess the influence of neighborhood safety on children's physical activity. Baba and Shimizu (2023) examine the impact of apartment vacancies on nearby housing rents over multiple times the study reveals that there is a significant negative correlation between apartment rent and vacancy duration. The aforementioned research majorly focused on neighbourhood safety on human physical and mental behaviours and activities.

Furthermore, Ogunrin (2019) explore a research on the impact of safety on rental values in Lagos. Safety is an important factor in determining rental values in Lagos, and that a safer neighborhood is associated with higher rental values. Lee *et al.*, (2023) investigated the use of neighborhood characteristics to predict vacancy types by comparing multi-scale conditions surrounding existing vacant lots. This study established the effect of neighborhood safety on property rental values. However, these highlighted researches only focused on neighborhood safety and the physical health of people, predicting vacancy rates, but neglecting the impact on rental property vacancy rates. Thus this study identify this gap and intend to filled at the end of this research, and as at the time of carrying out this study, there is no enough evidence of similar study being conducted in the study area. It is on this backdrop that this study tends to assess the impact of neighbourhood safety on rental property vacancy rate in Bida, Niger State.

2.0 Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research design, this method allowed for statistically analysis of data collected for the study which help examined the impact of neighbourhood safety on residential rental property vacancy rates in the study area. Bida, the study area was stratified into three distinct

neighbourhood densities (high, medium and low density) where a neighbourhood was finally selected from each strata; Dokodza in high density, Area 8 in medium density and FMC quarters in the low density neighbourhoods respectively. A total of 169 household were systematically selected from the residential rental properties and sampled across the three study area (50 in Dokodza, 56 in Area 8 and 63 in FMC quarters). A structured closed-ended questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection and the collected data on safety indicators of the neighbourhoods were descriptively analysed while the factors contributing to vacancy rate of rental properties and the hypothesis; H_0 : neighbourhood safety has no statistically significant impact on vacancy rate of rental properties was tested with the aid of linear regression model stated below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1BH + \beta_2HG + \beta_3HD + \beta_4PV + \beta_5UO + \beta_6PC \dots + \beta_9LG + \epsilon$$

Where;

Y= Vacancy Rate

BH = Burglary of homes

HG = High levels of gang activity

HD = Hate crimes/Discrimination

PV = Poor street lighting and visibility

UO = Unsecured vacant property

PC = Poor road conditions

LE = Lack cleanliness of environment

P = Pollution (Air, Water, Soil and Noise)

LG = Lack of green space maintenance

3.0 Results Presentation

3.1 Perception of Neighbourhoods Safety Attributes on Residential Rental Property

The results presented in Table 1 illustrate perception of residents of the sampled residential rental properties regarding the dominance of safety issues across the three neighbourhoods of Dokodza, Area 8 and FMC quarters. Respondents opinion were ranked with a five point likert scale of Highly Dominant (HD = 5) as the highest and Not Dominant (ND = 1) as the lowest level. The survey revealed widespread a varying level of residents' concern about safety, with high levels burglary of homes, hate crimes/discrimination, environmental health issues, and unsecured vacant properties reportedly dominant across all sampled neighbourhoods. In Dokodza, the most concerning safety issues are high level of gang activities (68% viewing it as high) while 66% perceived burglary of homes to be the second dominant safety issues in Dokodza. However, pollution appears the lowest safety issues as 18% of the respondents perceived it to be low and another 10% were of the opinion that environmental health issues is very low in Dokodza. Meanwhile, burglary of homes was perceived high in Area 8 with 78.6% supporting the notion of its occurrence, followed by 75% perceiving environmental health related safety as the second most dominant issue in Area 8; Poor street lighting alongside high level of gang activities as a security issues were least dominant with 7.1% attesting to its low occurrence. Finally in the low density neighbourhood of FMC quarters, the most dominant safety issues as perceived to be high by 63.5% of the respondents was burglary of homes, followed by unsecured vacant property with 58.7%

Saidu U. A., Mohammed J. K., Nathaniel, S.

attesting to its dominance; 9.5% and 7.9% of the respondents submitted that environmental health issues and pollution are less dominant around FMC quarters.

Table 1: Perceived Level of Neighborhood Safety Attributes in the Study Area

Location	Safety Attributes	HD	D	N	LD	ND	Total
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Dokodza	Burglary of homes	11 (22)	33 (66)	6 (12)	0 (0)	0 (0)	50 (100)
	High levels of gang activity	10 (20)	34 (68)	4 (8)	2 (4)	0 (0)	50 (100)
	Hate crimes/Discrimination	4 (8)	33 (66)	13 (26)	0 (0)	0 (0)	50 (100)
	Poor street lighting and visibility	4 (8)	22 (44)	20 (40)	4 (8)	0 (0)	50 (100)
	Unsecured vacant property	9 (18)	24 (48)	14 (28)	2 (4)	1 (2)	50 (100)
	Poor road conditions	4 (8)	30 (60)	16 (32)	0 (0)	0 (0)	50 (100)
	Environmental health issues	7 (14)	24 (48)	11 (22)	3 (6)	5 (10)	50 (100)
Area 8	Pollution (Air, Water, Soil and Noise)	4 (8)	20 (40)	17 (34)	9 (18)	0 (0)	50 (100)
	Burglary of homes	3 (5.4)	44 (78.6)	8 (14.3)	1 (1.8)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	High levels of gang activity	3 (5.4)	39 (69.6)	10 (17.9)	4 (7.1)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	Hate crimes/Discrimination	4 (7.1)	36 (64.3)	14 (25)	2 (3.6)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	Poor street lighting and visibility	0 (0)	29 (51.8)	23 (41.1)	4 (7.1)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	Unsecured vacant property	9 (16.1)	38 (67.9)	6 (10.7)	3 (5.4)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	Poor road conditions	0 (0)	25 (44.6)	29 (51.8)	2 (3.6)	0 (0)	56 (100)
FMC Quarters	Environmental health issues	12 (21.4)	42 (75)	2 (3.6)	0 (0)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	Pollution (Air, Water, Soil and Noise)	9 (16.1)	30 (53.6)	17 (30.4)	0 (0)	0 (0)	56 (100)
	Burglary of homes	16 (25.4)	40 (63.5)	5 (7.9)	2 (3.2)	0 (0)	63 (100)
	High levels of gang activity	12 (19)	13 (20.6)	37 (58.7)	1 (1.6)	0 (0)	63 (100)
	Hate crimes/Discrimination	9 (14.3)	35 (55.6)	17 (27)	2 (3.2)	0 (0)	63 (100)
	Poor street lighting and visibility	4 (6.3)	36 (57.1)	20 (31.7)	2 (3.2)	0 (0)	63 (100)
	Unsecured vacant property	16 (25.4)	37 (58.7)	9 (14.3)	1 (1.6)	0 (0)	63 (100)
FMC Quarters	Poor road conditions	4 (6.3)	36 (57.1)	20 (31.7)	0 (0)	3 (4.8)	63 (100)
	Environmental health issues	4 (6.3)	36 (57.1)	18 (28.6)	5 (7.9)	0 (0)	63 (100)
	Pollution (Air, Water, Soil and Noise)	4 (6.3)	25 (39.7)	26 (41.3)	6 (9.5)	2 (3.2)	63 (100)

Source: Field survey, 2024

3.2 Extent of Vacancy Rate in Residential Rental Properties in the Study Area

Table 4.2 revealed the average vacancy rates of residential rental properties in the study area locations exhibited fluctuations over the years. Dokodza had relatively stable vacancy rates, ranging from 3.6% in 2019 to 6.4% in 2023. The factors considered as a major threat to vacancy rates in Dokodza are economic conditions, screening process and regulatory. In 2014 and 2015, Area 8 had a comparatively high vacancy rate of 7.35%; in 2016, that percentage dropped to 6.2%. But in 2017, the vacancy rate rose sharply to 10.4%, and it stayed over 8% until 2020. In 2022, the vacancy rate in Area 8 peaked at 11.6%. The major factors affecting the vacancy rate in the Area 8 are safety and security concerns, accessibility and rent levels and affordability. F.M.C area experienced a decline in vacancy rates from 4.5% in 2014 to 1.8% in 2016. However, the vacancy rate increased to 11.5% in 2020 and then decreased to 4% in 2022. The common factors influencing the vacancy rates are screening process and regulatory, competitions from nearby housing options and economic conditions are seems to be it major criteria.

Table 2: Average Vacancy Rate of Residential Rental Properties in the Study Area

Location	2014 %	2015 %	2016 %	2017 %	2018 %	2019 %	2020 %	2021 %	2022 %	2023 %
Dokodza	4.5	4.7	3.8	4.3	4.3	3.6	5.4	6.3	5.6	6.4
Area 8	7.35	7.35	6.2	10.4	8.6	6.5	10.6	8.8	11.6	10.0
F.M.C	4.5	3.7	1.8	5.0	4.65	3.3	11.5	5.3	4.0	4.0

Source: Field survey, 2024

3.3 Determinants of Residential Rental Properties Vacancy Rate in the Study Area

Results presented in table 3 presents a summary of the determinants of residential property vacancy rates in the selected neighbourhoods of the study area. As observed, the vacancy rate of residential rental properties in Dokodza are mainly influenced by poor location and accessibility both ranked highest with (RII: 0.78, Ranked: 1st) followed by safety and security concerns (RII: 0.75, Ranked: 3rd). However, in Area 8, residential rental properties vacancy rates are primarily influenced by accessibility (RII: 0.72, Ranked: 1st), followed by safety and security concerns (RII: 0.71, Rank: 2nd), and property condition and age (RII: 0.67, Rank: 3). Finally, in FMC quarters the determinants of vacancy rates was observed to be poor location (RII: 0.82, Ranked: 1st), followed by safety and security issues (RII: 0.81, Ranked: 2nd) while accessibility (RII: 0.75, Ranked: 3rd). These results underscore the necessity for location-specific methods to address these concerns by highlighting the diverse factors that contribute to residential rental property vacancy rates across different locales.

Table 3: Determinants of Residential Rental Properties Vacancy Rate in the Study Area

Location	Sub-Variables	SA	A	U	D	SD	F	RII	Rank
Dokodza	Property condition and age	0	3	9	16	2	30	0.72	5 th
	Safety and security concern	2	0	2	23	3	30	0.76	3 rd
	Poor location	0	0	5	22	3	30	0.78	1 st
	Economic conditions	1	9	13	7	0	30	0.57	9 th
	Rent levels and affordability	2	0	11	17	0	30	0.68	8 th
	Competitions from nearby housing options	0	3	9	18	0	30	0.70	7 th
	Screening process and regulatory	0	4	6	20	0	30	0.71	6 th
	Accessibility	1	0	1	26	2	30	0.78	1 st
	Others	0	1	8	18	3	30	0.75	4 th
Weighted average = 0.72									
Area 8	Property condition and age	4	4	6	16	4	34	0.67	3 rd
	Safety and security concern	2	0	10	21	1	34	0.71	2 nd
	Poor location	3	2	12	16	1	34	0.65	8 th
	Economic conditions	3	6	18	7	0	34	0.57	9 th
	Rent levels and affordability	3	0	7	24	0	34	0.70	7 th
	Competitions from nearby housing options	1	3	10	19	1	34	0.69	5 th
	Screening process and regulatory	4	0	7	23	0	34	0.68	6 th
	Accessibility	4	0	2	27	1	34	0.72	1 st
Other(s)	6	0	1	25	2	34	0.70	4 th	
Weighted average = 0.68									
FMC Quarters	Property condition and age	5	5	3	21	3	37	0.66	7 th
	Safety and security concern	0	0	9	16	12	37	0.81	2 nd

Poor location	1	0	2	25	9	37	0.82	1 st
Economic conditions	1	6	15	15	0	37	0.63	8 th
Rent levels and affordability	1	0	10	25	1	37	0.73	5 th
Competitions from nearby housing options	5	4	10	18	0	37	0.62	9 th
Screening process and regulatory	1	2	7	25	2	37	0.73	5 th
Accessibility	4	0	2	25	6	37	0.75	3 rd
Others	5	0	2	23	7	37	0.74	4 th
Weighted average = 0.72								

Source: Field survey, 2024

3.4 Impacts of Neighbourhood Safety on Vacancy of Residential Rental Property in the Study Area

Findings of the study presented in Table 4 summarises the impact of neighborhood safety on residential rental property vacancy rates across the three selected neighbourhoods in the study areas: Dokodza, Area 8, and FMC quarters. In Dokodza, the model indicates a substantial correlation between vacancy rates and neighbourhood safety with an F-value of 10.001 and a statistically significant p-value of 0.043. However, in Area 8, neighbourhood safety has a considerable impact on property vacancy rates, as evidenced by the model's significance ($p = 0.041$) and F-value of 7.247. Meanwhile, in FMC quarters, the model suggests that property vacancies in this neighbourhood is not significantly impacted by neighbourhood safety is not significant ($p = 0.667$) with a low F-value of 0.689. According to this result, vacancy rates in Dokodza (high density) and Area 8 (medium density) are significantly influenced by safety concerns, but other variables could be more relevant in FMC quarters being a low density neighbourhood.

Table 4: Regression Table

Location	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Dokodza	Regression	.033	5	.007	10.001	.043 ^b
	Residual	.002	3	.001		
	Total	.035	8			
Area 8	Regression	.015	4	.004	7.247	.041 ^b
	Residual	.002	4	.001		
	Total	.017	8			
FMC Quarters	Regression	.022	5	.004	.689	.667 ^b
	Residual	.019	3	.006		
	Total	.041	8			

Source: Field survey, 2024

4.0 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study regarding respondents perception of neighbourhood safety is consistent with previous research in Nigeria and other African countries on neighbourhood safety perceptions

and how they affect residential rental properties. Research by Agheyisi and Aghedo (2021) in Benin indicated that activity of various gangs alongside burglary were the two major safety concerns determining property vacancies, rental value and stability around densely populated neighbourhoods. This same assertion was corroborated and observed in Area 8 and Dokodza where gang activity and burglary were perceived as a serious security concerns. This was earlier asserted in a study conducted in Johannesburg by Weimann and Oni (2019) reiterating that insecure vacant properties and environmental health are dominant in neighbourhoods with low income earners. In contrast, Babalola et al. (2020) asserted that air pollution is major safety issues influencing demand for real estate in Lagos which contradicts the observation in Dokodza and FMC quarters where pollution was perceived to be minor determinant of property vacancy.

Furthermore, the observed pattern of vacancy rate of residential rental properties in the study area are consistent with findings from related studies conducted in Nigeria and Africa, emphasising the importance of legal frameworks, economic situations, and security concerns in influencing vacancy variations. Similar to Area 8, where the highest vacancy rate of 11.6% was observed in 2022 as a result of security and rent affordability difficulties; this observation aligns with the submission of Nwachukwu (2023) in Abuja indicating that high vacancy rates in some metropolitan areas were driven by affordability constraints and safety concerns. Similar to the findings in Dokodza and FMC quarters, where screening procedures and economic conditions had a major impact, Tien (2019) in Vietnam found that economic variables and regulatory regulations were the main predictors of vacancy rates. The routine variation in the vacancy rate of rental properties around FMC quarters attaining the highest value in 2020 before falling again mirrors observable trends in Ghana by Adu-Gyamfi et al. (2022), where development of new residential properties and flexible finances contributed to vacancy rate instability. However, Bida is more influenced by economic circumstances than redevelopment which contradicts the submission of Weimann and Oni (2019) in Johannesburg, where urban renewal exercise by government significantly reduced the rate of property vacancy. Going by these comparisons, rental property markets in African cities are nevertheless shaped by similar factors including financial stability, safety, and regulations, even though vacancy patterns differ by region.

Furthermore, findings from the influencing factors of residential properties vacancy rate in the study area equally aligns with existing studies on the variation and dynamics of the housing market structures in Nigeria and elsewhere. The observation around Dokodza and FMC quarters implying the most important determinant is bad location corroborating the findings of Barreca et al. (2020) in Turin, where poor location and security issues are major cause of high vacancy rate in Italy. This is quite similar to the observation in Area 8, where accessibility was the most impactful determinant of vacancy rate, corroborating the submission of Dauda (2024) in Abuja where it was concluded that ease of access remains a crucial factor influencing rental properties demand and vacancy. The findings of Adewale et al. (2022) in Ibadan, where ageing homes contributed to more vacancies owing to diminishing tenant desire, are similarly consistent with the effect of property condition and age, as observed in Area 8. However, Weimann and Oni (2019) contended that urban renewal projects might lessen these impacts by boosting neighbourhood attractiveness

Saidu U. A., Mohammed J. K., Nathaniel, S.

and upgrading infrastructure, in spite of security concerns remaining a prevalent issue throughout the research locations. In line with the above, certain interventions like improved basic infrastructures alongside urban renewal initiatives could help reduce vacancy rate in affected neighbourhoods, despite location, accessibility and safety concerns remaining crucial determinants of rental vacancy rate.

Finally, findings of the study regarding the intricate impact of neighbourhood safety on vacancy of rental property align with similar studies across African countries and Nigeria. For instance, studies by Akinbobola (2022) and Agheyisi and Aghedo (2021) in Lagos and Benin demonstrated the influence of safety concerns on real estate, specifically in densely populated neighbourhoods known for high rate of crime and gang activities. This finding is consistent with the observation around Area 8 and Dokodza neighbourhoods where vacancy rate was found to be significantly impacted by neighbourhood safety. In the same vein, the observations from the findings of this study were further corroborated by Owusu-Ansah and Asante (2022) in Ghana submitting that the demand for rental housing is influenced by safety and security concerns by occupants. However, Opit et al. (2020) was of a contrary opinion that the impact of safety concern is not only limited to densely populated neighbourhoods as vacancy of rental properties in low density neighbourhoods are not immune to safety concerns from potential occupants. As observed, the observed variation indicated that while security challenges may influence vacancy rate of rental real estate, other factors like accessibility, economic stability and location plays significant role in certain situations. All of the highlighted observations underscores the need for a concerted and multidimensional approach towards tackling vacancy issues in line with the specific attributes of the neighbourhood.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

The study appraises the impact of neighbourhood safety on vacancy rate of residential properties across three distinct residential densities in Bida. The results highlighted the influence of neighbourhood safety on the rate of vacancy for residential rental property, especially in Dokodza (high density) and Area 8 (medium density), where safety concerns remains a major determinant in vacancy trends, while the influence of relatively low in the low density (FMC quarters). Findings further revealed that high rate of residential property vacancy are influenced by determinants like gang activity, burglaries alongside unfavourable condition of the environment while other factors, accessibility and economic determinants have limited impacts on vacancy rate of low density neighbourhoods like FMS quarters. Enhancement of neighbourhood security apparatus like adequate surveillance alongside routine security patrol and community-based initiatives should be given adequate attention and priority by policy makers and other stakeholders in a bid to mitigate the identified security challenges. Additionally, available infrastructures need to be improved while the ones not provided should be considered like street lighting at night alongside ample accessibility to increase mobility and overall liveability and convenience of residents which is capable of mitigating growing rate of vacant properties. Property developers and owners should equally endeavour to invest in advanced and contemporary security apparatus to further ensure sense of safety and belonging by potential occupants and renters

REFERENCES

- Adewale, P. O., Adewole, A. A., & Daramola, O. T. (2022). Housing Choice and Preferences of Civil Servants in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal for Environmental Sciences*, 1(1), 15-28.
- Adu-Gyamfi, A., Owusu-Addo, E., Inkoom, D. K. B., & Asibey, M. O. (2022). Peri-urban interface: An alternative residential location of low-income migrants in Kumasi, Ghana. *Cities*, 123, 103570.
- Agheyisi, J. E., & Aghedo, I. (2021). Neighborhood vulnerability to security threats in Benin City: The role of informal housing and the built environment. *African Studies Quarterly*, 20(4), 20-40.
- Akinbobola, B. A. (2022). Predicting the Determinants of Homicides Rates Across the ECOWAS Region, 1960-2020. *Developing Country Studies*, 12(7), 21-29
- Baba, H., & Shimizu, C. (2023). The impact of apartment vacancies on nearby housing rents over multiple time periods: application of smart meter data. *International Journal of Housing Markets and Analysis*, 16(7), 27-41.
- Babalola, O. D., Ibem, E. O., Olotuah, A. O., Opoko, A. P., Adewale, B. A., & Fulani, O. A. (2020). Housing quality and its predictors in public residential estates in Lagos, Nigeria. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 22, 3973-4005.
- Barreca, A., Curto, R., & Rolando, D. (2020). Urban vibrancy: An emerging factor that spatially influences the real estate market. *Sustainability*, 12(1), 346.
- Bourke, J. (2022). Military sexual trauma: gender, military cultures, and the medicalization of abuse in contemporary America. *Journal of War & Culture Studies*, 15(1), 86-105.
- Choi, K., & Lee, J. L. (2021). Citizen participation in community safety: a comparative study of community policing in South Korea and the UK. In *The Rise of Comparative Policing* (pp. 52-72). Routledge.
- Dauda, S. (2024). Access to Land: Effects on Housing Affordability in Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Civil Engineering, Construction and Estate Management*, 12(1), 19-40.
- Gerten, C., Fina, S., & Rusche, K. (2019). The sprawling planet: Simplifying the measurement of global urbanization trends. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 7, 140.
- Kiggins, C., & Pavol, A. (2023). The Effect of Neighborhood Safety on Childhood Mental and Behavioral Health Problems. https://corescholar.libraries.wright.edu/scholarship_medicine_all/107/
- Lee, R. J., Newman, G., & Van Zandt, S. (2023). Using neighborhood characteristics to predict vacancy types: Comparing multi-scale conditions surrounding existing vacant lots. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 50(9), 2594-2609.
- Malik, S., Roosli, R., & Tariq, F. (2020). Investigation of informal housing challenges and issues: experiences from slum and squatter of Lahore. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 35(1), 143-170.
- Nwachukwu, L. N. (2023). *Strategies for enabling private sector-driven affordable urban housing in Abuja, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nottingham). <https://eprints.nottingham.ac.uk/77078/1/Thesis%20Lilian%20final%20correction%201.pdf>

Saidu U. A., Mohammed J. K., Nathaniel, S.

- Odalonu, B. H. (2022). Worsening Insecurity in Nigeria and its implications on governance and national development. *African Journal of Humanities and Contemporary Education Research*, 5(1), 31-49.
- Ogbewe, R. I., & Ayodele, M. C. (2023). Might poverty be the greatest polluter?—exploring the link between poverty and environmental degradation in Nigeria. *Irish International Journal of Law, Political Sciences and Administration*, 7(6), 77-99.
- Ogunrin, O. S. (2019). *A parametric analysis of the thermal properties of contemporary materials used for house construction in South-west Nigeria, using thermal modelling and relevant weather data*. The University of Liverpool (United Kingdom).
- Ojo, A., & Ojewale, O. (2019). *Urbanisation and crime in Nigeria*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-3-030-19765-0.pdf>
- Olajide, S. E., & Lizam, M. (2016). Determining the impact of residential neighbourhood crime on housing investment using logistic regression. *Traektoriâ Nauki= Path of Science*, 2(12), 6-8.
- Opit, S., Carroll, P., & Witten, K. (2020). *Community acceptance of medium density housing development*. BRANZ.
- Owusu-Ansah, A., & Asante, L. A. (2022). Behavioural finance, property values and housing conversion in Urban Ghana. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 37(3), 1555-1577.
- Robinette, J. W., Piazza, J. R., & Stawski, R. S. (2021). Neighborhood safety concerns and daily well-being: A national diary study. *Wellbeing, space and society*, 2, 100047.
- Tien, N. H. (2019). Determinants of real estate bubble in Vietnam. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Management*, 2(2), 75-80
<http://digital.lib.ueh.edu.vn/handle/UEH/69639>
- Timperio, A., Veitch, J., & Carver, A. (2015). Safety in numbers: does perceived safety mediate associations between the neighborhood social environment and physical activity among women living in disadvantaged neighborhoods?. *Preventive medicine*, 74, 49-54.
- Toohey, K., & Taylor, T. (2023). Mega events, fear, and risk: Terrorism at the Olympic Games. In *The Olympics* (pp. 329-343). Routledge.
- Vitale, A. S. (2021). *The end of policing*. Verso Books. https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=1sRLEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR7&dq=ed+danger+and+growing+threats,+alongside+the++inability+of+the+police+to+provide+adequate+protection+that+have+led+to+the+emergence+of+neighbourhood+safety+challenges&ots=STPm4BllpX&sig=V5v1FKm-ZQRvkHT_M-asubrU0mA
- Wei, Y. D., & Ewing, R. (2018). Urban expansion, sprawl and inequality. *Landscape and urban planning*, 177, 259-265.
- Weimann, A., & Oni, T. (2019). A systematised review of the health impact of urban informal settlements and implications for upgrading interventions in South Africa, a rapidly urbanising middle-income country. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(19), 3608.